

Dyes Derived from Acenaphthenequinone. Part IV. Azines and Indigoid Vat Dyes.

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In continuation of the papers in this series (Sircar and Guha, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 335 ; Guha, *ibid.*, 1931, 582 ; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 423), this investigation was undertaken with a view to study if in the acenaphthenequinone series, azines could be prepared having acenaphthene nucleus on both the sides of the azine ring and if such arrangement, which will at the same time increase the complexity of the molecule, has got any effect in deepening the colours of the resulting azines.

This led the author to condense acenaphthenequinone and its various derivatives with 2:3-diaminoacenaphthene (Sachs and Mosebach, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2852) and the compounds obtained are acenaphtheno-, acenaphtheno-3-chloro-, acenaphtheno-3-bromo-, acenaphtheno-1-methoxy-, and acenaphtheno-3:4-dinitroacenaphthazines. These azines are yellow, brownish yellow and chocolate coloured crystalline substances and they dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid producing deep violet, violet blue and deep green solutions from which water reprecipitates the substances unchanged, quite suitable for dyeing on wool from an acid bath. The dyed shades on wool are yellow and chocolate. The yellow shade obtained on wool from acenaphtheno-acenaphthazine is in no way inferior to the same shade of the corresponding phenanthraquinone derivative (Sachs and Mosebach, *loc. cit.*). It is also observed that the introduction of NO_2 group in the molecule of acenaphtheno-acenaphthazine distinctly deepens the colour from the yellow to chocolate (*cf.* Fluoreno-acenaphthazines, Dutt, *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 1793).

β -Methoxyacenaphthenequinone and 1-methoxyacenaphthaphenazine melt at 221-22° and 187-89° respectively. Staudenger, Goldstein and Schlenker (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 342) record m. p. 215-16° and 182-83° respectively.

Lastly further studies in indigoid vat dyes in the Ciba Scarlet G. series (*cf.* Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, *loc. cit.*) have been made by condensing 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 541) with acenaphthenequinone, its chloro, bromo, and methoxy derivatives only ; the first three indigoid dyes easily

yield with alkaline hydrosulphite soluble blue vats from which the original scarlet products are regenerated on cotton by atmospheric oxygen. But in the case of the last named compound, the methoxy derivative, great difficulty was experienced in making use of it in the vat (*cf.* 2-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy) acenaphthylene-indigo, Staudinger and others, *loc. cit.*). The blue vat obtained in this case also on cotton turned only pink by treatment with air. Repeated attempts to secure the desired deep red shade on cotton were, however, unsuccessful. All the four substances dissolve in strong sulphuric acid producing deep green solutions from which the vat dyes are reprecipitated unchanged by the addition of water and as such each of them is suitable for dyeing on wool from an acid bath. The scarlet red shade obtained on cotton as well as on wool from the indigoid derivatives mentioned above are deeper than those of Ciba Scarlet G (Bezdzik and Friedlander, *Monatsch.*, 1908, 29, 306; and E. P. 344/1908) and its halogen derivatives (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

The azines, excepting the dinitro compound which does not melt but sublimes and the indigoid vat dyes on heating above their melting points volatilise unchanged producing coloured vapours of the individual product and deposit the dyes as pure compounds.

Further work in indigoid vat dyes in the acenaphthenequinone series is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acenaphthenoacenaphthazine.

This compound separated immediately as rectangular brownish-yellow crystals on heating acenaphthenequinone (0.273 g.) and 2:8-diaminoacenaphthene (0.276 g.) in 22 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid. It was first boiled with alcohol in which it was only sparingly soluble and then repeatedly extracted with acetic acid. The precipitate, obtained by the addition of water to the combined extract, was crystallised from amyl alcohol in elongated diamond shaped yellow crystals not melting below 315°. It is soluble in benzene,

xylene, pyridine or amyl alcohol, moderately soluble in acetic acid, sparingly soluble in ligroin, ethyl acetate and acetone. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a deep violet colour and dyes wool in yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: N, 8.81. $C_{24}H_{14}N_2$ requires N, 8.48 per cent).

Acenaphtheno-3-chloroacenaphthazine.—This compound was prepared similarly from 3-chloroacenaphthenequinone (0.216 g.) and 2:3-diaminoacenaphthene (0.184 g.) in 25 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and after being boiled with alcohol, it crystallised from pyridine in glistening yellow plates, not melting below 315° . It is soluble in nitrobenzene, aniline, xylene, pyridine, moderately soluble in amyl alcohol, acetic acid or carbon tetrachloride and dyes wool in yellow shades from an acid bath. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it forming violet blue solution. (Found: Cl, 9.54. $C_{24}H_{13}N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 9.73 per cent).

Acenaphtheno-3-bromoacenaphthazine was prepared in the same way as the preceding compound from 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (0.39 g.) and the diamine (0.276 g.) in 30 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and similarly purified and crystallised in yellow plates. It does not melt below 315° and it possesses properties similar to those of the last compound. (Found: Br, 19.34. $C_{24}H_{13}N_2Br$ requires Br, 19.55 per cent).

Acenaphtheno-1-methoxyacenaphthazine.—The brown solution, produced by boiling β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0.424 g.) and the diamine (0.368 g.) in 36 c.c. of glacial acetic acid for half an hour, was allowed to stand in the cold. The crystalline brownish-yellow precipitate, that separated after 1 hour was collected, purified first by boiling with alcohol and then by precipitation with water from the least quantity of boiling glacial acetic acid. The resultant flocculent precipitate on heating became granular. This was filtered, washed with hot water and crystallised from pyridine in beautiful hexagonal brownish-yellow plates, m. p. 293° . It is soluble in benzene, xylene, chloroform, acetic acid, pyridine and sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone and ether. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a violet blue colour and dyes wool in yellow shades. (Found: N, 8.1. $C_{25}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 7.77 per cent).

Acenaphtheno-3:4-dinitroacenaphthazine separated gradually in shining chocolate coloured rectangular crystalline precipitate on heating for 1 hour the dark brown solution, produced by bringing together 3:4-dinitroacenaphthenequinone (0.272 g.) and 2:3-diaminoacensphthene

(0.184 g.) in 75 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid. It was further purified by boiling successively with alcohol and acetic acid and finally crystallised from xylene in prisms; when strongly heated above 315° the azine sublimes. It is soluble in pyridine, xylene, aniline, sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride and amyl alcohol. It gives a deep green solution in strong sulphuric acid and dyes wool in chocolate shades from an acid bath. (Found: N, 13.68. $C_{24}H_{12}O_4N_4$ requires N, 13.33 per cent).

1-Methoxyacenaphthaphenazine.—The pale yellow solution produced by heating β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0.212 g.) and *o*-phenylenediamine (0.100 g.) in 52 c. c. of boiling glacial acetic acid for 20 minutes deposited no precipitate when cooled. The bulk of the solution was then reduced to 22 c. c. by the distillation of acetic acid and water added just to precipitate the product. It was redissolved by heating and allowed to cool. The separated needle shaped crystals were collected, washed with 50% acetic acid and hot water and finally recrystallised from dilute acetic acid in fine silky pale yellow needles, m. p. 187.88° (cf. Staudinger and others, *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 9.65. $C_{19}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 9.85 per cent).

2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigo.

A solution of acenaphthenequinone (0.364 g.) in 50 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid was mixed with 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) dissolved in 30 c.c. of hot glacial acetic acid. The mixture turned reddish-brown. On adding strong hydrochloric acid (8 c.c.) and shaking for 2-3 minutes silky scarlet red needle shaped crystals separated. The whole of the mixture was heated to boiling for 10-12 minutes to complete the reaction, filtered hot, washed with acetic acid and hot water. For purification it was boiled successively with alcohol and glacial acetic acid and finally crystallised from xylene in fine needles, m. p. 265.66° . It is soluble in chloroform, amyl alcohol, benzene, xylene, nitrobenzene, aniline and pyridine, difficultly soluble in acetic acid, sparingly soluble in acetone, alcohol, ether, insoluble in ammonia and caustic alkalis. It dyes cotton in

scarlet red shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat and wool in the same colour from an acid bath. (Found: S, 9.56. $C_{21}H_{12}O_2S$ requires S, 9.75 per cent).

2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'(3'-chloro)acenaphthyleneindigo, similarly prepared from 3-chloroacenaphthenequinone (0.65 g.) and 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 63 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 7 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid, crystallised from pyridine in clusters of scarlet red rectangular crystals, m. p. 284-85° (with previous shrinking at 281°). It dyes wool in bright pleasant scarlet red shade from an acid bath and cotton in deep scarlet red shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. All other properties resemble those of the preceding compound. (Found: Cl, 10.1. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 9.8 per cent).

2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'(3'-bromo)acenaphthyleneindigo, prepared in the same way as the two preceding compounds from 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (0.52 g.) and the methylhydroxy-thionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 51 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 5 c.c. of strong hydrochloric acid, separated from toluene in slender scarlet red rectangular crystals, m. p. 282°. It resembles the last compound in its properties. (Found: Br, 19.58. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2BrS$ requires Br, 19.65 per cent).

2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'(1'-methoxy)acenaphthyleneindigo.—The pinkish red solution, obtained by mixing β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0.424 g.) dissolved in 50 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid with methyl hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 25 c.c. of hot acetic acid, was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (12 c.c.) and shaken thoroughly. The solution turned beautiful deep violet red and immediately deposited deep scarlet red needles. It was then heated to boiling for 30 minutes. The precipitate was collected and purified by heating it with alcohol and with moderately strong acetic acid and crystallised from acetic acid as deep scarlet red fine needles, m. p. 279-80°. It dyes wool in deep red shades from an acid bath and in pink colour on cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. The solubility of this dye resembles that of the preceding compounds in this series. (Found: S, 9.26. $C_{22}H_{14}O_3S$ requires S, 8.93 per cent).

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